

Supplementary Table 1. Measurements collected during each experiment and used in the collated database, number of observations after selecting time points and averaging to get one measurement for each cow.

Exp. number ¹	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
Indicators of energy metabolism																				
BHB	187	420	255	296	378	184	731	741	0	0	425	0	2,125	0	1,563	1,716	449	1,476	1,717	1,043
NEFA ²	187	420	255	296	378	184	731	741	25	745	444	2,164	2,125	255	1,563	1,716	449	1,473	1,717	1,043
Glucose	187	420	4	296	378	184	731	741	25	745	350	0	0	255	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insulin	0	0	270	291	377	194	720	743	25	745	0	0	0	255	0	0	0	0	0	0
Growth Hormone	0	0	270	291	377	194	732	744	25	745	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IGF	0	0	270	290	377	194	732	744	25	745	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Leptin	0	0	0	0	375	193	726	0	25	0	0	0	0	255	0	0	0	0	0	0
BCS ²	140	234	255	215	349	185	584	639	162	1,296	649	1,965	3,978	475	1,378	1,419	411	1,469	4,638	701
Body weight	140	485	255	243	353	186	584	647	162	1,291	650	1,959	299	474	1,377	1,415	410	1,470	4,636	700
Indicators of protein metabolism																				
Albumin	187	420	0	0	0	0	731	741	0	0	350	2,164	2,125	0	1,563	1,715	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Total Protein	187	420	0	0	0	0	731	0	0	0	350	2,164	2,125	0	1,563	1,715	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
AGR ²	187	420	0	0	0	0	731	0	0	0	350	2,164	2,125	0	0	0	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Creatinine	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	350	0	0	0	0	0	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Urea	187	420	255	296	378	184	731	741	0	0	350	0	0	0	0	0	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Creatine Kinase	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Indicators of mineral status																				
Calcium	187	420	253	296	378	184	731	741	0	0	360	425	2,125	0	705	846	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Magnesium	187	420	255	296	378	184	731	741	0	0	349	2,162	2,125	0	705	846	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Phosphate	187	420	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	350	0	0	0	0	0	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Potassium	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Sodium	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Chloride	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Bicarbonate	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Indicators of liver function																				
Globulin	187	420	0	0	0	0	731	0	0	0	350	2,164	2,125	0	1,563	1,715	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
AST ²	187	420	4	0	378	184	0	0	0	745	350	2,164	1,955	0	1,563	1,715	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
GDH ²	187	420	4	0	378	184	0	0	0	745	350	2,164	1,955	0	0	1,715	449	1,474	1,001	1,043
Cholesterol	187	420	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	327	236	337	0	0	0
Bilirubin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
GGT ²	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	358	0	0	0	0	0	449	1,476	1,001	1,043
Liver TAG ²	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	352	0	135	0	392	0
Indicators of inflammation																				
IL-1B	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	327	236	337	0	0	0
IL-6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	327	236	337	0	0	0
Haptoglobin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	327	233	337	0	0	0
ROS ²	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	327	235	337	0	0	0
TAC ²	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	327	233	337	0	0	0
Uterine Health																				
PMN	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	112	213	802	0	267	239	35	341	469	110
Macrophage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	112	213	797	0	0	232	0	0	0	0
PVD score ²	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	114	213	821	0	268	247	36	345	795	111

¹Exp. Number = experiment number that corresponds to the experiments described in Table 1

²NEFA: Non-esterified fatty acids; BCS (1-10 scale; Roche et al., 2004); AGR: Albumin:Globulin ratio; AST: Aspartate aminotransferase; GDH: Glutamate dehydrogenase; GGT: gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase; TAG: triacylglyceride; ROS: reactive oxygen species; TAC: total antioxidant capacity; PVD: purulent vaginal discharge score (0-5 scale).